

Thermo-chemical Investigations on the Constitution of Acids in Solution.

BY

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It is well known that the properties of acids are generally explained by the presence of H-ions, and the strength of acids depends on the concentration of these ions. The undissociated acids possess, according to the classical theory, no activity. Some recent theories however postulate that concentrated acids, or even pure acids, are fully dissociated. Hantzsch¹ has studied the behaviour of undissociated acids and has advanced his extended theory of pseudo-acids, which can be summarised as follows :

1. The properties common to all acids (*e.g.*, action on indicators, on diazoacetic ester, on cane sugar, etc.) are not peculiar to the H-ions but are due to the presence of an ionogen H-atom (*i.e.*, an H-atom which has given up one electron to the oxygen of the acid radical). The H-atom is however not bound up with any single O-atom, but is loosely connected with as many O-atoms as possible. These are the so-called true acids and are represented graphically by

2. In the second class of acids the H-atom is bound down to one O-atom of the acid radical forming a hydroxyl group. These are the pseudo-acids which are represented graphically as

¹ Ber., (1917), 50, 1422; Z. Elektrochem., (1923) 29, 221; (1924) 30, 194

3. The third class of acids are the equilibrium acids, the typical representatives of this class being acetic and formic acids. Both the forms are here in dynamic equilibrium represented by

and this is affected by the particular solvent in which they are dissolved and by the concentration of the acid in it. Certain solvents like water move the equilibrium point to the right, while certain others like ether shift it towards the left.

4. The true acids form oxonium salts with water in the same way as they form ammonium salts with ammonia :

Water however being a very weak base, these salts are practically completely dissociated into their components even in moderately dilute solutions.

5. With ether and similar compounds the pseudo-acids form pseudo-salts or etherates :

In the case of strong acids like sulphuric or perchloric acids however, the true oxonium salts are formed :

This theory was based on the results of investigations on the nature of undissociated acids using the following four methods :—

1. The examination of the absorption spectra of the acids, their salts and esters in different solvents and comparison of the curves so obtained.¹

¹ Hantzsch, *loc. cit.*; Schäfer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, (1917) 97, 285.

2. Measurement of the velocity of reaction with diazoacetic ester.¹ It has been seen that the pure acids, which contain no H-ions react very vigorously with the ester giving out nitrogen, and that the ethereal solutions of the fatty acids, which contain either the pseudo-acids themselves or their pseudo-etherates are inactive.

3. The velocity of inversion of cane sugar in aqueous solutions. This is a reaction attributed solely to the presence of H-ions and used even for the estimation of H-ion concentration. It has, however, been found that concentrated aqueous solutions of acids, even though not fully dissociated, can effect inversion of cane sugar more readily than fully dissociated acids.

4. The action of acids on indicators like dimethylaminoazobenzene. This is seen to be a function of the solvent and the concentration. Most of the organic solvents can make the acids completely inactive against indicators in sufficient dilution.

In view of these facts it was of some importance to follow up the changes, which take place when an acid goes into solution, from the thermochemical point of view.

That the acids possess different properties in different solvents has often been shown. To give a well-known example, trichloroacetic acid reacts very vigorously with diazoacetic ester in pentane and water, giving out nitrogen according to the equations :

but is completely inactive in ethereal solutions even in quite moderate dilutions. Hantzsch explains this behaviour by the change in the constitution of the acid

¹ Dissertationen Leipzig, Teupel, Gutjahr, Schreiter, Karvó 1921 1924

under the influence of the solvent. In aqueous solution we have the true hydroxonium salt

while in ether we have the pseudoetherate

Now, when an acid goes into solution, a certain amount of heat (generally positive) is evolved. This can be measured and represents the algebraic sum of the different energy changes taking place in the system. In the first place we have to consider the purely physical phenomena where the solvent acts like a diluent. The expansion of the original volume of the acid to that of the solvent and the consequent work done, the molecular dissociation of the acid and of the solvent, and in some cases the electrolytic dissociation, are all phenomena which normally absorb heat. If therefore no other chemical action took place between solvent and solute, every substance would possess a negative heat of solution. It must therefore be concluded that some combination between the acids and the solvents takes place, in order to explain the positive heat of solution. Especially in the case of solvents containing oxygen, these solvates are the oxonium salts (either the true ones or the pseudo). The heat of solution alone can give, of course, no clue to the constitution of the compound formed, which can only be ascertained by means of the action on diazoacetic ester and indicators. The measurements of heats of solution help us, however, to form an idea about the affinity between the two substances and also about the stability of the compounds formed.

The usual method for the determination of the heats of solution requires large quantities of substances and still the results are not very accurate, the data for the same two substances given by different authors being sometimes very different. The method used in the following determinations was very simple and gave consistent and reproducible results. The details are given in the experimental part.

1. *Sulphuric Acid.*

The following Table 1 gives the heats of solution of sulphuric acid in various solvents. The numbers in this and in other similar tables denote gram-calories per gram-mol of the solute.

TABLE 1.

Heats of Solution of Sulphuric Acid.

Mols solvent per mol acid	Water	Alcohol	Ether	Diethyl sulphate	Nitrobenzene
1	6200
2	9000	
3	11200	
5	13500	.	11380	2450	1200
10	15200	15000	12800	2900	1500
15	15800	15750	13600	3050	1700
20	16200	16400	14360	3250	1880
25	16400	16800	14960	3300	2000
49	16800	17500	2290
99	17300

It will be seen that the heats of solution in water, alcohol and ether are much higher as compared to those obtained in the other two solvents. This acid, as is already known

is very highly associated (compare Ramsay and Shields)¹ who give a value of $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4)_{22,3}$ and the formation of monomolecular solvates would naturally involve the process $(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4)_n \rightarrow n\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, which would absorb a considerable amount of heat. The solvate-formation must therefore be a process which evolves a very great amount of heat. Kremann² has shown that at ordinary or even at slightly higher temperatures, no action takes place between sulphuric acid and ethyl alcohol and it was observed by me that ether and sulphuric acid do not react with each other even at 95°; and as the solutions of the acid are found to be active towards diazoacetic ester and indicators, the compounds formed must be the true oxonium salts:

Compounds like these have often been shown to exist. Von Frank³ has proved the existence of an etherate of sulphuric acid containing equal number of molecules of the two substances, by means of the discontinuity of the vapour-pressure curve of mixtures containing them. Etherates of diethyl and diamyl ethers have even been obtained in crystalline form at very low temperatures.⁴ The acid is easily soluble in nitrobenzene and the determinations of molecular weight⁵ have shown that it is bimolecular. The relatively small heat of solution means naturally a very small tendency to salt-formation, and also the moderately "basic" nature of the oxygen

¹ J. Chem. Soc. (1894), 65, 171.

² Monatsch. (1910), 31, 1051.

³ Diss. Leipzig, 1923.

⁴ Tschelinzew and Koslow, J. Russ. Chem. and Phys. Soc. (1914), 46, 708.

⁵ Ampola and Karlinfant, Gazz. Chim. Ital. (1896), 26, II, 76.

in nitrobenzene. In spite of this, a definite compound has been isolated¹ at 0° which has probably the structural formula :

In order to observe whether the decrease in the association of the solvent, which is known to take place at higher temperatures² has any effect on the heat of solution, experiments were also made at different temperatures (in water at 0°, 10°, 20°, 30°, and 40°, in alcohol at 0°, 10°, 20° and 30°, and in ether at 0°, 10°, and 20°). It was observed that the decrease in the heat evolved was about 2% for every 10° in the case of water and alcohol, and that in the case of ether, which is known to be monomolecular at all temperatures, the heat evolved was practically constant.

The supposition that oxonium salts are present in these solutions, cannot be proved directly in the above instances. It could, however, be proved indirectly by means of the study of the absorption spectrum of diethyl sulphide in concentrated sulphuric acid. Diethyl sulphide or thioether is very similar to diethyl oxide or ordinary ether in chemical behaviour and constitution, and has the advantage of showing strong absorption in the ultraviolet region; the solution in sulphuric acid is, however, practically transparent just like trimethylsulphonium bromide $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{SBr}$, the absorption of which has already been studied by Hantzsch.³ It can therefore be concluded that a similar compound also exists in the case of thioether having the formula $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{SH}\cdot\text{O}_3\text{SH}$. By analogy, we can deduce the

¹ Cherbuliez, *Helv. Chim. Acta* (1923), 6, 281.

² Ramsay and Shields, *Z. Phys. Chem* (1893), 12, 471.

³ *Ber.* (1919), 52, 1560.

structure of the compounds with water, alcohol and ether.

2. The Halogen Acids.

Thomsen's results¹ about the heats of solution of the three hydrogen halides are given below :

TABLE 2.

Heats of Solution of Hydrogen Halides in Water.

Mols water per mol acid	HCl	HBr	HI
1	5875
2	11365	18820	12540
3	13362	15910	14810
5	14959	17620	17380
10	16157	19100	18580
20	16756	19470	18990
50	17115	19820	19140

The values show that HI and HBr have a much greater affinity for water than HCl. In alcohol also, HBr is known to possess a higher heat of solution than HCl.² Hantzsch has shown by means of optical methods³ that HBr undergoes the following changes when dissolved in water :

oxonium

salt \longrightarrow hydration \longrightarrow ionisation

In the case of alcoholic and ethereal solutions, analogous phenomena can be assumed to take place, with the

¹ Landolt-Börnstein, Phys. Chem. Tabellen.

² Berthelot, Ann. chim. phys. (1876), 5, 2, 347.

³ Hantzsch, loc. cit.

difference that only HCl solutions of ether remain unchanged and allow the separation of definite etherates.¹ HBr acts upon ether slowly and HI very rapidly to form the respective ethyl esters and ethyl alcohol.² The observation of Jüttner,³ that the solubility of ether in water is increased by the presence of HCl, can be explained on the assumption that the etherate of HCl, having the nature of a salt, will naturally be more soluble in water than ether itself.

3. Nitric Acid.

TABLE 3.

Heats of Solution of Nitric Acid.

Mols solvent per mol acid	Water	Alcohol	Ether
5	6665	—	8600
10	7318	5750	9080
15	7400	7500	9940
20	7458	8450	9440
25	7480	8750	9480
30	7480	9000	9500

The results of the investigations on the optical behaviour of nitric acid can be summarised as follows: In dilute aqueous solutions the ultraviolet absorption is the same as that of the solutions of the nitrates, and contain the true hydroxonium salt $\text{NO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$; the alcoholic and ethereal solutions as well as the pure acid have an absorption very similar to that of the esters and hence these have the pseudo-formula:

¹ Steele, McIntosh and Archibald, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, (1909) 55, 152.

² Silva, *Ber.*, (1876) 9, 862; Lippert, *Ann. d. Chem.*, (1899) 276, 148.

³ *Z. phys. Chem.*, (1901) 38, 56.

The heat of solution in either alcohol or ether can therefore be taken to be the heat of formation of the pseudo-salt. The heat of solution in water is much smaller than in ether, and as the true hydroxonium salt is present in aqueous solutions, the transformation of the pseudo-acid into the true acid appears to be an endothermic process. The heat of solution in alcohol is slightly smaller than in ether and it shows, in agreement with the results of the optical investigation, that although the greater portion of the acid is present as a pseudo-salt, a very small percentage is still present as the true salt :

and has a lower heat of formation.

In ethyl and methyl nitrate, the acid dissolves without any heat of solution, and consequently with no change in the constitution.

4. Formic Acid.

TABLE 4.

Heats of Solution of Formic Acid.

Mols solvent per mol acid	Water	Alcohol	Ether	Acetone	Chloroform
5	..	670	1235	1860	-250
10	...	950	1305	2020	-320
15	...	960	1375	2130	-360
20	..	970	1420	2220	-390
25	...	990	1460	2300	-410
* Mols of Solvent necessary for inactivation.		20	10	9.2	...

* The last horizontal column in the table shows the amounts of the various solvents in mols which were required, to make one mol of the acid inactive against diazoacetic ester and indicators. The acid is then supposed to be completely transformed into the pseudo-form.

It is very remarkable that the heat of solution in water is so low that it could not be measured. The pure acid has been shown to contain¹ about 95% of the pseudo-acid and about 5% of true acid in equilibrium. The aqueous solution contains however much more of the true hydroxonium salt and we have to conclude that the dissociation of the acid absorbs very nearly the same amount of heat as is evolved by the formation of the salt. The highest heat is evolved in acetone solutions; and it is also this very solvent which "inactivates" the acid in the most concentrated solution. The heat of solution is therefore the heat of formation of the pseudo-salt :

Similarly the heats of solution in alcohol and ether are the heats of formation of the respective pseudo-salts.

5. Acetic Acid.

TABLE 5.

Heats of Solution of Acetic Acid.

Mols solvent per mol acid	Water	Alcohol	Ether	Acetone	Ethyl acetate	Benzene	Pentane
5	-80	...	+45	+650	...	-500	-1000
10	+85	...	+38	740	+51	-760	-1220
15	+115	..	+22	810	+24	-800	-1360
25	+208	.		900	...	-970	-1510
50	+275	.	.	980	-1680
Mols of solvent necessary for inactivation	5.1	2.2

¹ Hantzsch, *loc. cit.*

All the heats of solution are comparatively very small. In concentrated aqueous solutions the heat absorbed by the dissociation appears to be greater than the heat evolved by the formation of the hydroxonium salt; in dilute solutions, however, more of the salt is formed and an evolution of heat is observed. In the case of acetic acid also, the heat of solution in acetone is the highest, and this solvent also inactivates the acid most easily. Benzene and pentane, as fully saturated compounds, have very little or no tendency to solvate-formation, and the negative heat of solution is to be attributed solely to physical causes.

6. *Trichloroacetic Acid.*

TABLE 6.

Heats of Solution of Trichloroacetic Acid (liquid).

Mols solvent per mol acid	Water	Alcohol	Ether	Acetone	Benzene	Pentane	Nitrobenzene
5	1060
10	...	1270	...	5170	...	-6260	-800
20	...	1460	1810	5820	...	-6000	-460
30	...	1570	1550	5410	-6800	-5850	-120
40	400	1675	1690	5470	-6220	-5750	+100
50	800	1780	1790	5520	-5750	-5670	+350
100	2080	2180	2000	...	-5820	-5820	...
Mols of solvent necessary for inactivation	27	253	35

¹ The pure crystalline acid was used in all these experiments, and the known heat of fusion deducted from the heat measured, thus giving the heat of solution for the liquid acid.

The heat of solution in water is comparatively small, and the heats of solution in solvents not containing oxygen are negative. It is to be expected that the dissociation absorbs a great amount of heat, and at least in concentrated aqueous solutions, this heat is equal to the heat of formation of the true hydroxonium salt. In dilute solutions, the heats of solution are very nearly equal in solvents like water, alcohol and, ether, and the formation of the true as well as of the pseudo-salt appears to evolve the same amount of heat. The highest heat of solution is observed in acetone, although unlike formic and acetic acids, it is ether which inactivates the acid most easily. It has to be assumed, therefore, that acetone forms a true salt with trichloroacetic acid, having the formula :

Some experiments were also made to determine the heats of solution of various substances in concentrated sulphuric acid, (99%), the results of which are given in Table 7.

TABLE 7.

Heats of Solution in Sulphuric Acid.

Mols H ₂ SO ₄ per mol solute	Water	Methyl alcohol	Ethyl alcohol	Ether	Thio-ether	Acetic acid	Nitric acid
5	10740	...	11600	9580	...
10	11800	13900	12230	17070	14900	9900	7200
15	11700	14700	12500	17200	15200	10100	7850
20	11890	14800	12660	17370	15400	10220	8250
25	12120	14840	12780	17520	15600	10320	8550
30	..	14860	12880	17640	15800	10450	8750
50	.	14900	13160	17900	16340	10820	.

Here the acid is present in such large excess, that practically the whole of the solute might be said to be present in the form of a compound with the acid, and hence the heats evolved are the heats of formation of the various compounds. The comparatively small increase in the heat evolved, with increasing amounts of the solvent can thus be easily explained, while even in the most concentrated solutions, practically the whole of the solute has combined with the acid.

Ether possesses the highest heat of solution, and this shows that the diethyloxonium sulphate $\text{HSO}_4 \cdot \text{HO}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ has the highest heat of formation. Thioether has only a slightly lower heat of solution and shows once more the similarity in the behaviour of oxygen and sulphur compounds. As sulphuric acid is known to be active towards diazoacetic ester and indicators in all solvents, the compounds formed in all the above cases are the true salts. The fact that pure nitric acid has a positive heat of solution, can only be explained by means of the assumption that in comparison with more strongly acidic sulphuric acid, nitric acid functions as a "base." In the case of acetic acid, this is still more pronounced.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A. The calorimeter used for the experiments described above was of very simple construction. A small test tube was fitted up into another slightly larger one by means of a thin cork, and served as the actual calorimeter. The thermometer used was a standard one reading to one-tenth of a degree. The stirrer was a capillary tube drawn out and bent circular at the lower end. It was calibrated along the whole of its length, and was also used as a pipette to deliver known volumes of the liquid, whose heat of solution was to be measured,

into the calorimeter. The method was as follows: 10 c.c. of the solvent were taken into the calorimeter and after the temperature had become constant, a known volume of the acid was introduced by means of the stirrer-pipette. The solution was stirred uniformly and the maximum or the minimum temperature noted. With the help of the water-equivalent of the calorimeter, thermometer and stirrer, which had previously been determined by measuring the heat of neutralisation of dilute hydrochloric acid with alkali, and of the specific heat of the solvent, which was taken to be equal to that of the dilute solution, the total heat evolved or absorbed was calculated according to the formula :

$$Q = \{w \times (t_2 - t_1)\} + \{10ds \times (t_2 - t_1)\}$$

were

w = water equivalent, t_1 = initial temperature,

t_2 = final temperature, d = density of the solvent, and

s = specific heat of the solvent.

About 10 experiments were made in the case of each acid and the results plotted on graph paper, taking the mols of solvent per mol of solute as ordinates and the heat of solution per mol of solute as the abscissa. The numbers given in Tables 1-7 were then obtained by graphical interpolation.

B. The experiments on the inactivation of the acids were made as follows: Weighed portions of the acid and the calculated amounts of ethyl diazoacetate were brought together and dissolved in increasing quantities of the solvent until there was no evolution of nitrogen for 24 hours. This quantity of solvent was then taken to be the amount necessary to transform the acid completely into the pseudo-form. It was found to be practically identical

with that necessary to make the acid completely indifferent towards dimethylaminoazobenzene.

In conclusion, I wish to thank Prof. Dr. A. Hantzsch for the kind interest he has taken in the progress of the work.
